

CLINICAL AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL VARIANTS OF HYMENOLIPEDOSIS IN CHILDREN

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Relevance. Parasitic diseases are characterized by relatively slow development, chronic course, often long-term compensation. It is these features that are the main reason for underestimating the medical and social significance of these diseases. Parasitic diseases cause mental and physical development delay in children, reduce resistance to infectious and somatic diseases, reduce the effectiveness of vaccination, cause allergization of the body, inducing secondary immunodeficiencies. Under the influence of helminths and protozoa, homeostasis is disturbed in the body, pathological and immunopathological processes develop, which are adaptive in Uzbekistan.

Purpose of the study. Clinical and epidemiological characteristics of hymenolipidosis in children at various stages of the disease.

Materials and methods of research .For the period from 2018 to 2020. under our supervision were 60 children with hymenolipidosis under the age of 14 years. There were 28 (48%) boys, 32 (52%) girls. All of them were registered at the Bukhara Regional Infectious Diseases Hospital.

The diagnosis was based on detection of fecal preservation method (for protozoan cysts). In the case when the immediate study of the material is not possible, its conservation is applied. The principle of detection of intestinal protozoa in faeces by the preservation method is based on the fact that the preservative solution causes the fixation of protozoa with long-term preservation of the main morphological features of all stages unchanged, especially cysts (amoebae, Giardia, balantidia). The following preservatives are more commonly used: Safaraliyev's preservative: zinc sulfate - 1.65 g; concentrated formalin - 10 mg; phenol crystal. - 2.5 g; acetic acid conc. - 5 ml; methylene blue - 0.2 g; distilled water - 100 ml. Phenol is pre-melted in a water bath. The protozoa are stained blue. Turdyev's preservative: an aqueous solution of sodium nitrate 0.2% - 80 ml; Lugol's solution - 8 ml; concentrated formalin - 10 ml; glycerin - 2 ml; acetic acid conc. - 5 drops. Diagnosis of hymenolepiasis was carried out by coproovoscopy. Feces were taken 3 times with an interval of 2-3 weeks due to the peculiarities of the development cycle of the causative agent of hymeno-lepidosis - pygmy tapeworm. Moreover, it is necessary to examine fresh material (morning fecal sampling). Statistical analysis of the data was carried out using the Microsoft Excel spreadsheet program, which was formed in accordance with the requirements of the study.

Results and their discussion. When studying the results of the study, it was revealed that the epidemiological characteristics of hymenilipedosis in children in the districts of the Bukhara region. Due to a significant increase in the number of cases of hymenilipedosis in children, the likelihood of contact of an infectious disease doctor with hymenilipedosis infected patients is also increasing. With hymenilipedosis in children, various manifestations of the disease often occur with damage to the internal organs. The IgE index in patients with AR with hymenolepidoses after treatment significantly exceeds (3.5 times) the IgE values in

the control group, although it significantly decreases relative to the index before treatment, which is observed against the background of significantly low B-lymphocytes in the course of the disease. Changes in the content of ASL were similar - their level decreased, the decrease was significant for ASL against TAG of the trachea and intestines, however, their values were higher than the parameters of the control group. Infectologists, as well as other specialists, already have to take an active part in the diagnosis, treatment of hymenilipedosis in infected individuals, preventive work, which, of course, will require knowledge of the characteristics of the course of hymenilipedosis in children . At the reception, there may be patients who do not know about the infection of hymenilipedosis, hiding - for well-known reasons - infection; patients in the incubation stage, which can also become a source of infection for other patients. To prevent infection of personnel, one must know the ways and factors that implement the transmission of hymenilipedosis in children, and the provision of assistance must be carried out in compliance with the necessary safety measures and with strict observance of the rules for disinfection and sterilization of used instruments. Thus: Hymenolipedosis contribute to the violation of the immune system, cause the emergence and development of various secondary diseases, the severity of which depends on the course of the underlying disease. The identified symptoms of hymenolepiasis are clear evidence of how this invasion is systemic in nature, has a pathogenic effect on the organs and systems of the body. It is easy to guess (and the latest literature data testify to this) that such a high incidence of hymenolepiasis and its pronounced pathogenic effect on the body is possible with a weakened immune system of children, weakness of nonspecific protective functions of their body.

Conclusion. The maximum clinical effect was achieved by us with the use of complex treatment, which included antiallergic and antiparasitic therapy. Antiallergic therapy led to a rapid improvement in the condition of patients, and antiparasitic therapy consolidated this effect. The most pronounced positive dynamics according to rhinopneumometry data was also observed after complex treatment. Complex antiallergic and antiparasitic treatment has a pronounced immunological effect, activates the severity of the immune reaction, switches the nature of the immune reaction to suppressor, and thereby contributes to a more rapid relief of the allergic process in the body. The effectiveness of such a formulation of work is due to the fact that most children under 7 years old attend preschool institutions and almost all children aged 7-15 attend schools. In addition, when visiting territorial children's institutions, it is possible to cover the appropriate sanitary and educational work with the parents of children, who willingly make contact and subsequently bring even healthy children for parasitological examination.

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